

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

SPON1 (Spondin-1)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	10418 / Q9HCB6
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD, AMP-AD
TREAT-AD Authors	Jesse Wiley ¹ , Greg Cary ² and the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center
Therapeutic Area(s)	Alzheimer's disease
Document version	1.0
Document version date	May 2024
Citation	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11167949
Affiliations	¹ Sage Bionetworks, Seattle, WA, USA ² The Jackson Laboratory, Bar Harbor, ME, USA

USEFUL LINKS

TREAT-AD

[Visit TREAT-AD](#)

Learn more about the TREAT-AD centers and mission

Agora

[Visit Agora](#)

View Alzheimer's disease target results explorer

AD Knowledge Portal

[Visit AD Knowledge Portal](#)

View available target enabling resources

CONTENTS OF TEP

Bioinformatic analysis: Target source & hypothesis

Validated antibodies & generic knockout cell lines: YCharOS antibody characterization report

TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including SMOC1 and SFRP1.

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 3.93 (rank #494, 98th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being

evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 3.15 out of 5 (rank #4061, 98th percentile). The individual score components include 1.18 of 3 for genetics, and 1.97 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of SPON1, both protein and RNA, is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. SPON1 is annotated to GO terms from the Structural Stabilization, Proteostasis, APP Metabolism, and Metal Binding and Homeostasis domains.

Overall	rank	pctl	GeneticsScore	OmicsScore
3.153	4061	83.74	1.182	1.971

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer's Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low confidence measures of expression. The expression of SPON1 is confidently detected in astrocytes, vascular and leptomenigeal cells (VLMC), and both excitatory and inhibitory neuron sub-types within this dataset.

The expression of SPON1 is confidently detected in astrocytes, vascular and leptomenigeal cells (VLMC), and both excitatory and inhibitory neuron sub-types within this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

SPON1 was identified in a large proteomic study of AD patients as a component of a module that ranked highest for cognitive deficits and pathology (1). Consequently, SPON1 was selected as a target for resource development within TREAT-AD, which includes purified protein, characterized antibodies, and a bioinformatics analysis of AD risk association and cell-type expression patterns. Given the potential SPON1-APP interaction promoting synapse formation (see below), we hope these resources will provide valuable resources to new investigators to expand their focus into SPON1-related topics for potential novel mechanisms of AD translational intervention.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

SPON1, encoded by the Spondin 1 gene, is a large 90 kilodalton multifunctional secreted protein known for its diverse roles in various biological processes. At the structural level, SPON1 is characterized by several distinct domains, including several thrombospondin type 1 repeats (TSRs), low-density lipoprotein receptor class A (LDLRA) repeats, and a reelin-like domain (2). These domains enable SPON1 to interact with a wide range of binding partners and participate in multiple cellular functions. The thrombospondin type 1 repeats (TSRs) are particularly important for SPON1's adhesive and signaling functions. These repeats mediate interactions with cell surface receptors, such as integrins, and extracellular matrix components, facilitating cell adhesion and migration (2). The binding and association of SPON1 with extracellular matrix plays a role in synapse formation and stabilization of cellular interactions promoting viable neuronal wiring in development(3-5). The developmental synapse formation is promoted by three separate mechanisms of action: commissural axon outgrowth promotion, inhibition of neural crest cell adhesion, and contact repulsion of developing motor neuron axons(6). Additionally, the LDLRA repeats contribute to SPON1's ability to modulate axon outgrowth, fasciculation, and guidance during neural development (6).

SPON1 plays crucial roles in both neural and non-neural tissues. In neural tissues, SPON1 promotes axon outgrowth and fasciculation, maintains cell adhesion, and guides neuronal migration (2, 6). In non-neural tissues, SPON1 regulates cell-matrix adhesion and modulates processes such as muscle attachment to the epidermis (2). These diverse functions highlight the importance of SPON1 in orchestrating tissue morphogenesis and homeostasis during development. Furthermore, SPON1 has been implicated in the pathogenesis of Alzheimer's disease (AD). Several studies have identified associations between SPON1 gene variants and AD-related phenotypes, including cognitive decline, as well as minor contributions to risk for developing AD (7, 8). Functional studies have revealed potential mechanisms by which SPON1 may influence AD pathology. For example, SPON1 binds to amyloid precursor protein (APP) and inhibits its cleavage by β -secretase, thereby modulating the production of amyloid-beta (A β) peptides implicated in AD pathogenesis (9). Interestingly, APP is also involved in neuronal synapse formation, being present in both developing axon growth cone lamellipodia and dendritic spines(10, 11). Loss of APP is associated with a decrement in synaptic development, both in terms of morphological maturation and number(10-12). Given the SPON1-APP association, these two genes may function together during development to promote synapse formation and may represent a new mechanism to target for synaptic stabilization in aging to forestall the onset of neurocognitive decline and dementia.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Validated Antibodies & Generic Knockout Cell Lines

The YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report guides researchers to select the most appropriate antibodies for SPON-1. The YCharOS antibody characterization pipeline uses knockout (KO) cells to perform head-to-head comparisons of available commercial antibodies for SPON-1 by immunoblot (Western blot), immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence. The cell line background was chosen based on the adequate expression of the target protein.

[SPON1 antibody characterization report](#)

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further investigation of the role of SPON-1 in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

References

1. Johnson ECB, Carter EK, Dammer EB, Duong DM, Gerasimov ES, Liu Y, et al. Large-scale deep multi-layer analysis of Alzheimer's disease brain reveals strong proteomic disease-related changes not observed at the RNA level. *Nat Neurosci*. 2022;25(2):213-25.
2. Woo WM, Berry E, Hudson ML, Swale RE, Goncharov A, Chisholm AD. The *C. elegans* F-spondin family protein SPON-1 maintains cell adhesion in neural and non-neural tissues. *Development*. 2008;135(16):2747-56.
3. Feinstein Y, Borrell V, Garcia C, Burstyn-Cohen T, Tzarfaty V, Frumkin A, et al. F-spondin and mindin: two structurally and functionally related genes expressed in the hippocampus that promote outgrowth of embryonic hippocampal neurons. *Development*. 1999;126(16):3637-48.
4. Burstyn-Cohen T, Tzarfaty V, Frumkin A, Feinstein Y, Stoeckli E, Klar A. F-Spondin is required for accurate pathfinding of commissural axons at the floor plate. *Neuron*. 1999;23(2):233-46.
5. Klar A, Baldassare M, Jessell TM. F-spondin: a gene expressed at high levels in the floor plate encodes a secreted protein that promotes neural cell adhesion and neurite extension. *Cell*. 1992;69(1):95-110.
6. Tzarfati-Majar V, Burstyn-Cohen T, Klar A. F-spondin is a contact-repellent molecule for embryonic motor neurons. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2001;98(8):4722-7.
7. Sherva R, Tripodis Y, Bennett DA, Chibnik LB, Crane PK, de Jager PL, et al. Genome-wide association study of the rate of cognitive decline in Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimers Dement*. 2014;10(1):45-52.
8. Shah AM, Myhre PL, Arthur V, Dorbala P, Rasheed H, Buckley LF, et al. Large scale plasma proteomics identifies novel proteins and protein networks associated with heart failure development. *Nat Commun*. 2024;15(1):528.
9. Park SY, Kang JY, Lee T, Nam D, Jeon CJ, Kim JB. SPON1 Can Reduce Amyloid Beta and Reverse Cognitive Impairment and Memory Dysfunction in Alzheimer's Disease Mouse Model. *Cells*. 2020;9(5).
10. Young-Pearse TL, Chen AC, Chang R, Marquez C, Selkoe DJ. Secreted APP regulates the function of full-length APP in neurite outgrowth through interaction with integrin beta1. *Neural Dev*. 2008;3:15.
11. Martinsson I, Capetillo-Zarate E, Faideau M, Willén K, Esteras N, Frykman S, et al. APP depletion alters selective pre- and post-synaptic proteins. *Mol Cell Neurosci*. 2019;95:86-95.
12. Wu CI, Vinton EA, Pearse RV, 2nd, Heo K, Aylward AJ, Hsieh YC, et al. APP and DYRK1A regulate axonal and synaptic vesicle protein networks and mediate Alzheimer's pathology in trisomy 21 neurons. *Mol Psychiatry*. 2022;27(4):1970-89.

We respectfully request that this document is cited using the DOI value as given above if the content is used in your work.